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CONTENTS

Editorial board	iii
Instruction to authors	iv
Editorial	v
Knowledge, Attitude and Preparedness of Teachers towards Inclusive Education in Ejisu - Juaben Municipality in Ashanti Region of Ghana MprahKwadwo Wisdom, Joseph AbabioDwomoh, Maxwell PeprahOpoku, Isaac Owusu and Joseph Ampratwum	1-15
Status of Rehabilitation Services for Children with Intellectual Disability in the State of Jammu & Kashmir: A Comparative Situational Analysis Dr. Rohnika Sharma & Prof. A.T. Thressiakutty	16-23
Need Assessment of Mothers Having Children with Intellectual Disabilities S.R. Githa & Saumya Chandra	24-31
Inclusive Education in India: Assessing the Systemic Readiness! Dr. Bharti	32-44
Status of Higher Education of Students with Disability in India: A Gujarat Profile Dr. H. S. Mistry	45-55
Indian Sign Language (ISL)	56-57
Success Story of Sri. Sathasivam Kannupaiyan	58-59
Braille Machine Review: BRAILLO 650 SW: An Ultra-Modern Braille Embosser	60-61

Status of Higher Education of Students with Disability in India: A Gujarat Profile

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Abstract

Right to education is a universal human right as mentioned under Article 26 (1) of universal declaration of human rights. From this point of view, on no grounds can any individual be denied the right to education. Many committees and commissions in India recommended general education for the children with disabilities and steps have also been taken by the government in this direction by implementing the integrated and inclusive education schemes for the children with disabilities. The Sarva Siksha Abhiyan (2007) report notes a steady increase in the numbers of students with disability in schools from 6,83,554 in 2002-03 to 26,21,077 in 2007-08. So, the question emerges here is what is the status of students with disability (SwDs) in higher education? This paper aimed at finding out the answer of the question by conducting the study on status of higher education of students with disability in Gujarat state of India. Nine general universities were selected as a sample and data were collected through the questionnaire. The study reveals very low enrollment of the SwD in the universities of Gujarat and lack of proper facilities, supporting services and provisions for the SwD. This paper discusses the findings and highlights the educational implications of the results.

Introduction

The right of all children to develop to their maximum potential is inherent in the philosophy of democracy. The Indian Education Commission (1964-66) also recommended the education of Children with Disabilities (CwD) in regular schools. The National Policy on Education (NPE, 1986) focused special attention on the education of CwD for achieving the goal of EFA. The urgency of the need to educate and rehabilitate to the Persons with Disabilities (PwD) is not only based on altruistic and humanistic motive, but it also has an economic and political dimension. The uneducated and untrained CwDs grow up into adults who are economically dependent and this influences the quality of life.

Some individuals can learn fast and some of them learn slowly but they can complete the task with reasonable and supporting devices. These individuals have special learning needs due to their learning problems arising out of physical or psychological deficit. Due to significant developments in medical science, technology and education, the individual with special learning needs can also be educated using special instructional methodology, instructional material, learning aids and equipment specific to their special learning needs. It also requires additional teaching competencies in the teachers. These special learning needs have given rise to the component of education known as Special Education. The World Health Organization (WHO, 1980) has defined the terms 'Handicap', 'Impairment'

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and 'Disability' through the publication of the International Classification of Impairment, Disability and Handicap (ICIDH). Based on this model, categories of special education may be listed as mentally retard, hearing impairment, visual impairment, orthopedic impairment, learning disability, speech impairment and giftedness.

Globally, special education has evolved through five stages viz. stage of neglect, stage of pity and compassion, stage of special school, stage of mainstreaming and integration and stage of the concept of special needs. In India, several committees and commissions have made various recommendations for the education of CWD. During the pre-independence, Sargent Report (1944) looked first time for the education of CWD whereas after independence, Indian Education Commission (1944-66), National Policy for Children (1974), NPE (1986), Ramamurthy committee (1992), National Policy on Education Review Committee (NPERC, 1992), Programme on Action (POA, 1992) and National Policy on Persons with Disability (NPPWD, 2006) have made useful recommendations for the education of CWD in general schools. Apart from these, five major legislative acts (Mental Health Act, 1987; Rehabilitation Council of India, 1992; Persons with Disability Act, 1995; National Trust Act, 1999 and Right To Education, 1999) have significant impact on the education and welfare of PWD in India. These legal mandates have helped to shape the comprehensive National Action Plan for Inclusion in Education of the Children and PWD (MHRD, 2005).

An estimated 10 percent of the world's population experiences some form of disability

The PWD Act (1995) indicates that PWD should have access to education at all levels. In higher education, UGC is supporting universities and colleges in the country to involve in special education activities to empower PWD. The MHRD announced Comprehensive Action Plan for the IECYD in 2005. So, disability friendly unit, scholarships similar as given to the SC/ST students, special aids and assistive devices etc facilities should be available in all higher education institutes for making higher education accessible to the PWD. UGC is supporting universities and colleges in the country to involve in special education activities to empower PWD. The UGC had started the scheme of assistance to universities/colleges for Higher Education for Persons with Special Needs (HEPSN) since the Ninth Five-

9,97,687 SWD at lower primary level.

or impairment (WHO Action Plan, 2006-2011). The number of PWD is increasing due to population growth, ageing, emergence of chronic diseases and medical advances that preserve and prolong life, creating overwhelming demands for health and rehabilitation services (Srivastava and Khan, 2008). According to the census 2001, there were 21.9 million PWD in India which was 2.13% of the total population of India. Out of them, only fourty nine percent were literate whereas only six percent of the literate population with disability were receiving higher education i.e. graduation and above. Also from the Tables of Statistics of School Education (2007-08) it was found that the enrollment figure of the CWD is decreasing as the schooling level increasing as only 2,990 Students with Disabilities (SWD) were studying at higher secondary level against the total enrollment of 9,97,687 SWD at lower primary level.

Year Plan which is an environment institutions to enrich experiences of PwL the capabilities of I improving accessibility to enrich learning, of assistance and according to the India's youth population in the least 3160,000 should be in the of India. However 3.6 lakh disabled been studying at Universities and (reality into an estimated 98.8 percent of its higher educational population were illiterate. The Gujarat was very low literacy rate of 10,45,465 (100 percent of Gujarat, 5,64,9 population were illiterate. The and 1, 80,592 (100 percent of total literacy rate of India. Gujarat Court and Training (GC) of the disabled the in 1992 under SI

Year Plan which is basically meant for creating an environment at the higher education institutions to enrich higher education learning experiences of PwD. Creating awareness about the capabilities of PwD, construction aimed at improving accessibility, purchase of equipment to enrich learning, etc., are the broad categories of assistance under this scheme. However, according to the UGC (2006), six percent of India's youth population is in Universities and Colleges. Proportionately, based on the most conservative estimate for the disabled youth population in the country (NSSO, 2003), at least 3160,000 Youth with Disabilities (YwD) should be in the Universities and Colleges of India. However, just 1.2 percent of the 3.6 lakh disabled youth, who should have been studying according to India's norm for the general youth population, are in the Universities and Colleges. It brings the stark reality into an established truth that India's higher educational system is not accessible to 98.8 percent of its YwD.

According to the Census, 2001, out of the 10,45,465 (100 percent) disability population of Gujarat, 5,64,907 (fifty four percent) PwD were literate while remaining forty six percent were illiterate. The males and female literacy population were 3, 84,315 (36.76 percent) and 1, 80,592 (17.27 percent) respectively. The literacy rate of the disability population in Gujarat was very low as it stood at 3.59 percent of total literacy population of Gujarat and 9 percent of total literacy disability population of India.

Gujarat Council of Educational Research and Training (GCERT) looks after education of the disabled through the IEDC Cell created in 1992 under State Education Department

and its functioning under GCERT since 1998. Convergence with NGOs has strengthened the implementation of the IEDC scheme in Gujarat. According to the NUEPA Report of Elementary Education in India: Progress towards UEE (2011), there were total 69,471 CwD enrolled in general elementary schools of Gujarat during the year 2008-09. Out of these, 41,450 were boys whereas 28,021 were girls. According to the SSA survey undertaken in the year 2009-10, a total of 66,746 CwD were enrolled under the IEDC scheme in the primary schools of different districts of Gujarat (SSA Report, 2009). According to the survey of Mistry and Panigrahi (2013) in nine UGC recognized and funded universities of Gujarat, there were a total 188 SwD enrolled on the three percent reservation quota in nine universities of Gujarat during the year 2008-09.

Need and justification of the study

For a very long time CwD were thought to be incapable of receiving education. This was despite the fact that many distinguished PwD have made significant contribution to science, arts and literature. To quote a few illustrations, Homer the immortal Greek poet was blind. Saunderson, who was also a blind person, did most of the mathematical work. Luise Braille who was a blind from his early childhood developed a revolutionary system of reading and writing for the blind. Stephen Hawking who is severely physically handicapped is regarded as one of the most leading physicist of the world. Beethoven a famous musician was a deaf person, Hellen Keller who was deafblind from early childhood became a graduate and wrote number of books. So we could say that PwD are not dis-abled but specially-abled.

The NPE (1986) has laid special emphasis on the removal of disparities and to equalize educational opportunities by attending to the special needs of those who have been denied equality so far. The main objective was to integrate the physically and mentally handicapped with the general community as equal partners, and to prepare for normal growth and to enable them to face life with courage and confidence. Due to insufficient documentation, researches in the past fifty years, both India and abroad, are poorly informed about India's special educational needs and disability issues in the nineteenth century. Until about 1947, the then provincial governments had taken sporadic interests in the education and training of the handicapped, usually by giving adhoc grants to schools and other institutions for the handicapped, and it emerges that it was voluntary efforts that played a pioneering role in the field of education and social service (Gupta, 1984). Jangra et. al. (1988) mentioned that research in special education is a neglected area of operation and it requires strengthening considerably if education of the SWD is to be made an effective proposition. More research on accommodations, services and the level of support given to SWD relative to their disability they possess is needed (Difaligo, 2005). Ongoing research programmes on disability are limited in India. Although, one of the objectives of NPPWD (2006) and the PWD Act (1995) is to support the research in prevention and management of disability, the major focus is on the social upliftment, monetary benefits (like job opportunities, exemption from taxes, pensions, etc.) and providing rehabilitation facilities to disabled people (Walia, 2010).

The result of the survey conducted by the National Council for Promotion and Employment of Disabled Persons (NCPEDP, 2001) revealed that only 1,635 SWD were enrolled in 129 universities of India. Among them fifty two universities were not following the three-percent reservation rule available for the PWD. In each Indian University, thousands of students are studying every year, if we measure the expected enrollment figure of SWD based on three percent reservation quota availed to them then the enrollment figure of SWD should be more than the revealed which indicates that total enrollment of SWD in the universities of India is very less. According to the UGC (2006), six percent of India's youth population is in Universities and Colleges. Proportionately, based on the most conservative estimate for the disabled youth population in the country (NSSO, 2003), at least 3160,000 disabled youth should be in the Universities and Colleges of India. However, just 1.2% of the 3.6 lack disabled youth, who should have been studying according to India's norm for the general youth population, are in the Universities and Colleges. It brings the stark reality into an established truth that India's higher educational system is not accessible to 98.8% of its disabled youth. Also, Walker (2008) reported that very few researchers have looked upon about the issues of university/college going SWD.

Present study focuses upon the enrollment figure of SWD, various problems of the SWD, their family background, their need and the supporting services provided by the universities of Gujarat State to the SWD. The survey of NCPEDP (2001) reveals that out of the 129 respondent universities of India,

- only Veer Narm (SGU), Surat n while other uni it is important t of PWD in the u to bring the con the enrollment in Gujarat. The universities of It provisions and f So it is equally im and facilities p to the SWD. He has been though SWD that focus the universities, facilities for SWL
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only Veer Narmad South Gujarat University (SGU), Surat responded from the Gujarat while other universities did not respond. So it is important to study the enrollment figure of PwD in the universities of Gujarat in order to bring the comprehensive picture regarding the enrollment of SwD in higher education in Gujarat. The UGC (2009) notified to all universities of India for strict implementation of PwD Act (1995) and for providing the provisions and facilities mentioned in the act. So it is equally important to study the provisions and facilities provided by the universities to the SwD. Hence, in the light of above, it has been thought of to undertake a study on SwD that focuses on their enrollment figure in the universities, and status of provisions and facilities for SwD in the universities of Gujarat.

Objectives of the study

- To study the enrolment figure of the students with disability in the universities of Gujarat for the year 2008-09.
- To study the status of facilities, provision of schemes, special equipment and services for the students with disability in the universities of Gujarat.

In the present study, an attempt is made to seek answer to the following questions.

Research questions

- What is the status of SwD in the universities of Gujarat?
- Whether the enrolment of SwD is as per the 3% reserved quota availed for them?
- What is the extent of utilization of facilities offered by the universities of Gujarat?

All these questions therefore, call for more in-depth study in order to present a real picture regarding higher education of the SwD.

Delimitation

The present study is delimited to the 9 general universities of Gujarat recognized by UGC and receiving government fund. Further, the study was delimited to the SwD enrolled on 3% reservation quota in various courses of 9 general universities of Gujarat during the academic year 2008-09.

Research design

The present study adopted survey design and surveyed the status of SwD and status of facilities, provisions and supporting services for the SwD in the nine general universities of Gujarat.

Sample

There were about thirty universities functioning in the Gujarat during the academic year 2008-09. As the present study was delimited to the UGC recognized and funded universities of Gujarat, total nine UGC recognized universities of Gujarat receiving the Government fund were selected purposively.

Tool

Self-constructed questionnaire was used for the present study. The questionnaire consisted items related to the enrolment figure of students with disability, information regarding their disability, constitutional policies related to the admission of the students with disability, provision of schemes, special equipment services and facilities provided by the universities to the students with disability.

Data collection procedure

The data were collected through the official website of the universities of Gujarat and personal visit of selected 9 general universities. The investigator personally visited each of the selected universities of Gujarat and

- collected the required information regarding the university, teaching departments, facilities provided by them to SWD and their enrollment figure. Investigator also approached them to give permission for the data collection from the teaching departments of their university. After getting the permission from the Vice Chancellor's office, investigator had visited Post Graduate Unit of the selected nine universities which having every academic communications with the teaching departments and collected information regarding the university, teaching departments, overall enrollment figure of the students, enrollment figure of the SWD for the academic year 2008-09, facilities provided by the university to the SWD, name of teaching departments etc. After getting the list of the affiliated teaching departments from the each of the university, the investigator visited each and every teaching department of all the nine universities and collected data regarding admission process, admission to SWD, total number of teaching staff, total number of enrolled student, number of registered SWD along with the category of disability, general and special facilities provided to the SWD by the department, name of the SWD registered in the department along with their residential address with contact number, year and course he/she is studying etc.
- Data analysis**
Frequencies and percentage were counted. Content analysis technique was also employed wherever applicable.
- Major findings**
- Findings related to enrollment figure of SWD**
 - The overall enrollment of the SWD in the universities of Gujarat was very less

compared to the three percent reservation rule. The difference between observed and expected enrollment was found to be 81.09 percent. The enrollment of SWD was found more in the Arts and other disciplines than Science and Commerce. Among three categories of disability, majority of the SWD (88.83 percent) were having orthopaedic impairment. The enrollment of SwVI and SwHII were found very less whereas there was no enrollment of the SwMD.

100 SWD were studying at Post-graduate and Master of Philosophy (M. Phil.) / Doctor of Philosophy (Ph.D.) level. All the SWD studying at M.Phil./Ph.D. level were having orthopaedic impairment.

Category wise, majority (65.1 percent) of the SwOI and SwVI (75 percent) were studying at post-graduate level whereas majority of the SwHII (80 percent) of the total five SwHII) were studying in diploma courses.

Findings related to facilities provided to SWD by the universities

All the nine universities were giving admission to SWD and following three percent reservation rule since the inception of the rule.

The scholarship scheme was common to all students and SWD have to get it on merit basis.

No financial assistance was provided by any of the nine universities.

Bus/train concession pass and hostel facilities were provided by the some of the universities but these facilities were also available to all students.

Discussion
From the enrollment figure of the universities (1995) strictly finding that SWD are in university (2001). So it is not improved for strict implementation and recommendation that PWD in Universities to courses have reason could be implemented certain steps for

- Hostel facilities provided to SWD were found to be 81.09 percent. The enrollment of SWD was found more in the Arts and other disciplines than Science and Commerce.
- Among three categories of disability, majority of the SWD (88.83 percent) were having orthopaedic impairment. The enrollment of SwVI and SwHII were found very less whereas there was no enrollment of the SwMD.
- 100 SWD were studying at Post-graduate and Master of Philosophy (M. Phil.) / Doctor of Philosophy (Ph.D.) level. All the SWD studying at M.Phil./Ph.D. level were having orthopaedic impairment.
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- All the nine universities were giving admission to SWD and following three percent reservation rule since the inception of the rule.
- The scholarship scheme was common to all students and SWD have to get it on merit basis.
- No financial assistance was provided by any of the nine universities.
- Bus/train concession pass and hostel facilities were provided by the some of the universities but these facilities were also available to all students.

- Hostel facility was not free of cost. The M. S. University of Baroda, Gujarat University and KSKV Kutch University were providing writer facility to the SwVI whereas two universities Gujarat University and KSKV Kutch University were providing extra time facility to SwD for writing in examination but sign language interpreter facility was not available in any of the university.
- No special equipments like disability friendly computer softwares, books in Braille, appropriate desks and chairs and disability aid/equipment like wheelchair, tricycle, hearing aid were available in the universities.
- It was also found that, none of the nine universities were having councillor for the SwD.
- All the nine universities were neither providing any kind of training to the teachers to deal with SwD nor employing trained teachers in special education.

Discussion

From the findings of **objective I**, low enrollment figure of the SwD made it clear that the universities were not following the PwD Act (1995) strictly. This finding also supports the finding that only 1.2 percent of the 3.6 lakh YwD are in universities or colleges (NCPEDP, 2001). So it is clear that the situation has still not improved and the Government's effort for strict implementation of PwD Act (1995) and recommendation of NPPwD (2006) that PwD will be provided access to the Universities to pursue higher and professional courses have still remained only on paper. The reason could be lack of monitoring about the implementation of rule. There is need to take certain steps for improving the situation of SwD

at higher education level. Strict implementation of PwD Act (1995) in all the universities and monitoring of the reservation should be made compulsory. Also collaboration between universities and special as well as general schools can be of great benefit to bring PwD in higher education. One of the reasons for the low enrollment of SwD could be lack of awareness among them about the three percent reservation rule and other provisions available for their education. Every universities and departments need to advertise about the number of reserved seats available for the PwD alongwith the other reserved quota like OBC, SC and ST. Developing transition goals from school to college/university and a course of study prior to entering into higher education will provide opportunities for YwD to take the necessary course work as per their interest, aspiration, capabilities and abilities. Out of the three category of disability, majority of the enrolled SwD were found with orthopaedic impairment whereas there was no enrollment in the category of SwMD during the year 2008-09. Even the enrollment figure of SwVI and SwHI was also very low. So it could be said that the lack of awareness about these disabilities was a major hindrance for their higher education.

From the findings of **objective II**, it was found that all the nine universities were following three percent reservation rule availed for SwD but the actual enrollment figure was far too less, thus more efforts are needed for strict implementation, advertisement of the number of seats available for the SwD. All the universities except GU were giving scholarships. But this scholarship was common to all students not only for SwD. Alur (2004) rightly

Educational implications of the present study

The findings of the present study have following implications.

- For improving the status of PwD in higher education, concerted efforts by government and society at large should be made for strict implementation and continuous monitoring of PwD Act (1995) in terms to give them opportunity to pursue higher and professional courses. Also awareness programmes related to the provisions for PwD, different disabilities among them, teachers and other persons will be of great help to improve the educational status of PwD at all level. Government should make efforts to bring the school community and higher educational institutes closer to each other so that higher education institutes can admit the SWD directly from the integrated and special schools. Career guidance programmes to the SWD at high school level can be useful to divert them in their interested areas.
- UGC and higher education institutes should look whether the provisions and facilities granted for the PwD are available in the higher education institutes in reality or not.
- Supporting aids and appliances like disability aids and equipments like wheel

mentioned that lack of political lobby greatly affect the PwD in India as SC/ST persons are receiving maximum benefits because of the strong political lobbies. Free of cost or separate hostel facility should be made available to the SWD who are facing mobility problems due to their disability so they can attend the classes regularly. This could be of immense help in the socialization and mainstreaming of SWD as the study of Sharma (2004) revealed that learning can increase by placing the CWMR in the hostel and they will get exposure. Writer facility for SwVI, interpreter facility for SwHII, extra time for writing in examination facilities and special equipments like disability friendly computer software, books in Braille, appropriate desks and chairs and disability aid/equipment like wheelchair, tricycle, hearing aid should be made available in all the universities. Collaboration between universities and NGOs working in the field of disability could be great help in this direction. It is difficult for the higher education institutes to appoint specially trained teachers only for the SWD but universities can arrange orientation or in-service training regarding the special education for the teachers so that they can deal with the students with various disabilities and can teach them by keeping in mind their disability. This will be benefited as the Landrum (2008) reports that if teachers had experience with the disability or were provided with support than they were more willing to include SWD. Also, nothing has been done on the recommendations of NPPWD (2006) that universities, colleges and professional institutions will be provided financial support to establish Disability Centre to take care of educational needs of SWD and they will be encouraged to make classrooms,

chairs, tri provided can cope disability recommer softwares, desks and available monitorin in all high a lot for th from the l

Conclusion

The stud universities perspective of help-seeking t and reasons enrollment of was observed the SWD was percent reser Also the unav greatly affecte that governm to make the the PwD and their enrollm and to make in the a was observed facing financi problems anc need of prop inputs to over The study rev interest in the continue thel doctoral leve

chairs, tricycle, hearing aids should be provided to the needy SwD so they can cope up with their disability. Also disability friendly supporting services recommended by the UGC like computer softwares, books in Braille, appropriate desks and chairs etc. should be made available. Strict implementation and monitoring of all these supporting services in all higher education institutions will help a lot for the SwD to take maximum benefit from the higher education.

Conclusion

The study dealt with the SwD in the universities of Gujarat from a broader perspective of enrollment, problems, needs, help-seeking behavior, availability of facilities and reasons of their success/failure. In the enrollment of the SwD in the universities, it was observed that the enrollment figure of the SwD was very low compared to the three percent reservation quota availed for them. Also the unavailability of the required facilities greatly affected to their enrollment. This seems that government and universities have failed to make the higher education accessible to the PwD and lot need to be done to increase their enrollment figure in higher education and to make the higher education accessible to the PwD.

In the area of problems and needs, it was observed that majority of the SwD were facing financial problems and some academic problems and accordingly they were having need of proper finance and some academic inputs to overcome their respective problems. The study revealed that most of the SwD had interest in the higher studies and wanted to continue their study upto post-graduate and doctoral level but the financial difficulties,

lack of facilities and some of the problems were affecting greatly their education so they were worried about completion of their study. This study also reveals that the insecure future was one of the reasons for their lack of interest in higher studies. Government think tank and policy makers should think for some alternatives in this regard. It was also observed that, generally, SwD did not differ much to the normal students at higher education level as the reasons of their poor academic performance were generally same as the reasons of normal poor academic performers. However, adequate facilities and supporting devices related to the disability could improve their performance to a large extent.

Thus on the basis of the present study it can be concluded that, most of the policies, recommendations regarding the education of PwD have not been properly implemented. Facilities for the education of YwD should be made available on time. Awareness about the different disabilities, provisions and facilities among the disabled, teachers and other members of the higher education could be of great help for the education of the YwD. Attention to these aspects, if provided timely and immediately, will lead to ensuring the expected improvement in the higher education of the PwD. If they will be encouraged to take higher education and prepare them for a career then in turn they will become productive and successful citizens.

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